

Preliminary Conceptual Design of a Compliant Forceps to be Utilized for Rotator Cuff Arthroscopic Surgery

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Abstract. This study presents the preliminary design of compliant detachable forceps that is equipped with dual-suture mechanism to address key limitations of conventional arthroscopic rotator cuff repair surgery. Dual suturing in single pass aims to reduce total number of steps in target surgery procedure. Compliant nature of the forceps will enable it to be utilized in the procedures of grasping/suturing as a gripper, and at the same time anchoring as a transformable/detachable anchor. Proposed method has the potential to shorten operative time, decrease the physical burden on the surgeon, and minimize complications associated with knot-tying and instrument maneuverability.

Keywords: Rotator Cuff Repair, Arthroscopic Surgery, Compliant Forceps, Dual Suturing

1 Introduction

The rotator cuff is a group of four muscles and their tendons that stabilize the shoulder joint and enable arm elevation and rotation. Rotator cuff tears occur when one or more of these tendons are partially or fully detached from the humeral head. While acute tears may result from trauma or sudden overload, most injuries develop gradually due to age-related degeneration, repetitive overhead activities, or reduced vascularity of the tendons. Epidemiological studies show that the prevalence of full-thickness tears increases significantly with age, reaching over 36% in individuals in their 80s, and many tears remain asymptomatic, especially in older populations [1]. Clinical symptoms often include shoulder pain, weakness, and limited range of motion, with nocturnal pain being a common complaint. Diagnosis is established through clinical examination supported by imaging modalities such as X-ray, MRI, or ultrasound.

Treatment strategies aim to reduce pain and restore shoulder function. Approximately 80–85% of patients benefit from conservative management, including rest, NSAIDs, physiotherapy, activity modification, and corticosteroid injections. Surgical repair—whether open, mini-open, or arthroscopic—is recommended in cases of persistent symptoms, large tears, significant functional loss, or acute traumatic injury. Arthroscopic repair has become the preferred minimally invasive technique, offering comparable clinical outcomes to open surgery with reduced soft-tissue disruption [2]. Postoperative rehabilitation, consisting of immobilization followed by progressive passive and active exercises, is essential for optimal recovery. Despite generally favorable outcomes, complications such as stiffness, infection, nerve injury, and tendon re-tear may occur, particularly in elderly individuals or those with poor tissue quality [4]. Arthroscopic minimally invasive surgery places substantial physical and technical demands on the surgeon. Working within a highly confined space, the surgeon must manipulate commercially available forceps and perform complex knot-tying maneuvers with limited instrument mobility. In current procedures sutures are integrated on the bone anchors, thus once the anchor is inserted into target location, the sutures should be brought to outside in order to be loaded again into the commercially available forceps. In order to avoid their entangling different ports should be utilized for each set of sutures. Once the forceps are loaded outside with one set of sutures, arthroscope should be inserted through the entry port to complete the suturing on the torn muscles. Note that it should also be removed to proceed tying the knot at outside the port. Due to the requirement of frequent tool relocations during the operation (removal and reinsertion of the different forceps, port changes to vary the approach angles etc.), sutures may become entangled, prolonging the procedure and increasing surgeon fatigue, which can ultimately compromise surgical outcomes. To address these potential issues, this study proposes a preliminary design of detachable compliant forceps equipped with a dual-suture mechanism in order to reduce total number of procedural steps in minimally invasive Arthroscopic surgery. The main motivation of the study is to enable the operation to be executed by using only a single port insertion, thus reducing the period of overall surgical procedure drastically. Instead of using single suturing from multiple ports, and positioning the anchor afterwards via reinsertions, proposed tool carry out necessary tasks with its transformable gripper style anchor capable of dual suturing and anchoring at the same time.

2 Preliminary Design

Dual-suture mechanism of the proposed compliant forceps design (see Fig. 1) reduces the number of portals required during arthroscopic surgery from three to two. Under standard practice, an arthroscope is inserted through one portal, while two separate forceps are introduced through the remaining portals, due to the fact that the surgeon typically needs two forceps to perform the suturing procedure. The compliant forceps equipped with a dual-suture mechanism enable the surgeon to complete mentioned suturing process through a single portal. When the jaws of the forceps grasp the torn muscle, two offset suture needles are inserted into the tissue, unlike the commercially available forceps single needle. The forceps then retrieve the sutures passing from the opposite side of the muscle. At this stage, the forceps effectively function as a suture anchor [3], [4], [5] by locking its gripper structure. The surgeon pulls the muscle together with the forceps to determine the appropriate insertion point for the already closed and locked suture anchor on the bone. Once this position is identified, the forceps and sutures are advanced into the bone in a manner similar to a conventional suture anchor, after which the forceps are detached from the tool handle concluding the anchoring operation.

Fig. 1. Preliminary Conceptual Design of the Compliant Forceps

This study presents a compliant forceps design incorporating a dual-suture mechanism to address key limitations of conventional arthroscopic rotator cuff repair. Traditional procedures require multiple portals and the simultaneous use of two forceps, increasing instrument congestion, surgeon fatigue, and the likelihood of suture entanglement within the confined sub acromial space. The proposed mechanism enables the complete suturing process to be performed through a single portal by integrating two offset suture needles into a single compliant forceps structure. This approach not only reduces the number of required portals but also streamlines the suturing workflow by allowing the forceps to function temporarily as a suture anchor [3], [4], [5]. As a result, the method has the potential to shorten operative time, decrease the physical burden on the surgeon, and minimize complications associated with knot-tying and instrument maneuverability. Future works will be focused on the mechanical optimization of the forceps, experimental validation through bench-top mockup and cadaveric testing, and evaluation of its clinical feasibility across diverse tear morphologies.

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